

1 Insights from an Electro-Mechanical Heart Failure Cell Model:
2 Role of SERCA Enhancement on Arrhythmogenesis and Myocyte
3 Contraction

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10

11 **ABSTRACT**

12 *Background and Objective*

13 Structural and electrical remodeling in heart failure predisposes the heart to ventricular
14 arrhythmias. Computer modeling approaches, used to complement experimental results, can
15 provide a more mechanistic knowledge of the biophysical phenomena underlying cardiac
16 pathologies. Indeed, previous in-silico studies have improved the understanding of the electrical
17 correlates of heart failure involved in arrhythmogenesis; however, information on the crosstalk
18 between electrical activity, intracellular Ca²⁺ and contraction is still incomplete. This study aims
19 to investigate the electro-mechanical behavior of virtual failing human ventricular myocytes to
20 help in the development of therapies, which should ideally target pump failure and arrhythmias
21 at the same time.

22 *Methods*

23 We implemented characteristic remodeling of heart failure with reduced ejection fraction
24 by including reported changes in ionic conductances, sarcomere function and cell structure (e.g.
25 T-tubules disarray). Model parametrization was based on published experimental data and the
26 outcome of simulations was validated against experimentally observed patterns. We focused on

27 two aspects of myocardial dysfunction central in heart failure: altered force-frequency
28 relationship and susceptibility to arrhythmogenic early afterdepolarizations. Because biological
29 variability is a major problem in the generalization of in-silico findings based on a unique set of
30 model parameters, we generated and evaluated a population of models.

31 *Results*

32 The population-based approach is crucial in robust identification of parameters at the core
33 of abnormalities and in generalizing the outcome of their correction. As compared to non-failing
34 ones, failing myocytes had prolonged repolarization, a higher incidence of early
35 afterdepolarizations, reduced contraction and a shallower force-frequency relationship, all
36 features peculiar of heart failure. Component analysis applied to the model population identified
37 reduced SERCA function as a relevant contributor to most of these derangements, which were
38 largely reverted or diminished by restoration of SERCA function alone.

39 *Conclusions*

40 These simulated results encourage the development of strategies comprising SERCA
41 stimulation and highlight the need to evaluate both electrical and mechanical outcomes.

42

43 **Keywords**

44 Heart failure; electro-mechanics; computational modeling; twitch force; early
45 afterdepolarizations; SERCA

46

47 **Abbreviations**

48 AP: action potential; APD: action potential duration; CaT: Ca²⁺ transient; CaTA: Ca²⁺ transient
49 amplitude; DevF: developed force; EAD: early afterdepolarization; EMw: electro-mechanical
50 window; FFR: force-frequency relationship; HF: heart failure; SR: sarcoplasmic reticulum; TTP:
51 time to peak force; RT: recovery time.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of mortality worldwide and the incidence of heart failure (HF), eventually their common fate, is increasing due to population aging. Reduced ejection fraction and electrical instability are the most damaging consequences of HF; ideally, treatments should address them both. However, therapeutic efficacy can vary between patients due to genotype differences, suggesting the need to consider intrinsic variability in studies.

The complexity of biological systems makes integration of specific experimental findings into disease patterns very difficult. Currently, mathematical biophysical models are widely used to fill this gap; they provide a powerful tool for mechanistic interpretation and prediction, the latter including the virtual test of pharmacological compounds. Most previous in-silico investigations focus on electrophysiology [1–3], however, excitation and contraction closely interact and abnormalities in both coupled processes in HF determine the disease pattern. The development of myofilament contraction models [4,5], and more recently with human data [6], allows the integration of cellular mechanics with the electrical part. Indeed, this electro-mechanical approach has contributed to the understanding of arrhythmogenesis triggered by oscillations in action potential duration, alternans, or drugs [7–10], but not in the setting of HF.

Both structural and functional changes contribute to the propensity for ventricular arrhythmias in HF. Altered transcription and/or post-transcriptional modification (e.g. phosphorylation) account for abnormality of channel and transporters function, which are also affected by disruption of membrane microdomains [11]. Among them, the loss of transverse tubules (T-tubules) has remarkable consequences on Ca^{2+} dynamics because of loss of the spatial relationship between L-type calcium channels (LTCC), ryanodine receptors (RyRs), and $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchangers (NCX). Models incorporating all these factors allow to reproduce the observations in failing myocytes more accurately and obtain more realistic predictions.

Cardiac contractile reserve assures myocardial contraction with changes in heart rate, however it is impaired in HF. The relationship between heart rate and developed force (force-frequency relationship, FFR) depends on the competition between several Ca^{2+} fluxes; thus, its

79 steepness (“slope”) integrates the function of the main cellular Ca^{2+} transports and buffers.
80 Normally positive in the human heart, FFR slope is reduced, or even inverted, in HF [12,13].
81 Interestingly, increased susceptibility to arrhythmias has been correlated with negative FFR [14].
82 Early afterdepolarizations (EADs) are a frequent arrhythmogenic mechanism in HF and they are
83 an integrated phenomenon as well, resulting from the crosstalk between sarcolemmal
84 conductances and intracellular Ca^{2+} dynamics.

85 We used, for the first time, a comprehensive electro-mechanical single-cell model to assess
86 which among the abnormalities described in HF may mostly contribute to contractile deficit, FFR
87 depression and arrhythmogenesis by EADs. The “electromechanical window” (EMw) a clinically
88 measurable parameter reported to quantify arrhythmogenic risk [15] was also considered.
89 Computational simulations were performed using a population-based approach, wherein a
90 population of models is obtained by implementing variability of input parameters to produce a
91 spectrum of phenotypes recapitulating biological variability. Variability of model output (electro-
92 mechanical responses) allowed identification of influential input parameters by using statistical
93 criteria, which would be impossible with a fully deterministic approach.

94

95 **2. METHODS**

96 **2.1. Electro-mechanical model of heart failure**

97 A widely accepted human action potential model, the ToR-ORd model [16], which includes
98 14 ionic currents for electrophysiology and intracellular Ca^{2+} dynamics, was selected to be
99 coupled to an active force (sarcomere) model [6] to fully simulate excitation-contraction (EC)
100 coupling and mechano-electrical feedback, exactly as recently done in [10], where some
101 mechanical parameters were re-adjusted to improve the outputs of the human model. When
102 integrating both models, intracellular Ca^{2+} acts as the intermediate agent between the electrical
103 and the mechanical activity. The model includes the dyadic subspace, an intracellular
104 microenvironment resulting from contiguity of the sarcolemmal and sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR)
105 membranes, essential in the interaction between the effectors of EC-coupling. The dyadic space

106 (defined by the subscript ‘ss’) and the bulk cytosolic compartment (defined by the subscript ‘i’)
107 were analyzed separately, an approach that proved essential in mechanism interpretation (see
108 below). Stretch-activated sarcolemmal channels were also included in the model for
109 completeness; however, they are inconsequential in the present work because the simulations
110 were performed under isometric conditions. MATLAB code of ToR-ORd model [16] was used
111 as the basis to implement all the modifications.

112 The electro-mechanical model was applied to generate virtual “control” (considered
113 healthy) and “failing” myocytes. The HF myocyte was obtained by introducing in the healthy one
114 the electrophysiological remodeling changes detailed by Gomez et al. [17] (Supplementary Table
115 S1), molecular changes observed in failing myocytes extracted from hearts with reduced ejection
116 fraction. In brief, SERCA maximal flux velocity was downregulated by 55% and NCX one
117 upregulated by 60%, Ca^{2+} leak from the SR compartment (SR leak) increased by 30% and RyRs
118 channel sensitivity to SR Ca^{2+} increased ($K_{\text{rel,Ca}}$ was reduced by 20%). Ion currents were also
119 affected by HF: the conductance of I_{NaL} (represented as an independent component), was
120 upregulated by 30% and its time constant τ_{hL} was increased by 80%, I_{to} , I_{K1} and I_{NaK} conductances
121 were downregulated by 60%, 32%, and 30%, respectively. Finally, CaMK activity was increased
122 by 50%.

123 Furthermore, loss of T-tubules, a functionally relevant feature of cellular remodeling, was
124 introduced in the HF model accordingly to Sanchez-Alonso et al. observations [18]. T-tubular
125 structure reduction partially disrupted the dyadic space, redistributing part of LTCC and NCX
126 proteins from the dyadic sarcolemma to that delimiting the bulk cytosolic space. As a
127 consequence, part of the Ca^{2+} release units (LTCC-RyR pairs) were uncoupled, thus increasing
128 the proportion of “orphaned” RyR channels. In addition, based on experimental findings in
129 myocytes with dilated cardiomyopathy [18], LTCCs located in the sarcolemma were maximally
130 phosphorylated by CaMKII. Exact details about the implementation of these changes in the
131 myocyte model can be found in the Supplementary Material.

132 Heart failure remodeling also affects the contractile apparatus, being the elevation of
133 myofilament Ca^{2+} sensitivity the most common alteration. According to experimental

134 observations [19,20], this change in Ca^{2+} sensitivity was modeled by reducing by 30% the Ca^{2+}
135 concentration required for half-maximal Troponin C binding ($[\text{Ca}]_{\text{T50}}$ in Land et al. [6]).

136 All simulations were performed in MATLAB (R2020b, MathWorks) and were run on
137 endocardial-type cells at steady state stimulation (i.e. after 500 beats in each condition). Active
138 force was obtained under isometric conditions, i.e. with no changes in sarcomere length.

139

140 **2.2. Population of models**

141 To account for biological variability and experimental uncertainty, our analysis was based
142 on the comparison between populations of “myocytes” (i.e. models). To this end, an initial
143 population of 1000 healthy myocytes was generated by randomly applying scaling factors to a
144 total of 29 parameters (18 of channels/transporters and 11 of sarcomeric proteins, see
145 Supplementary Tables S2 and S3) to the baseline model, so that each myocyte had a different set
146 of randomly combined parameters. We assumed that parameters were normally-distributed and
147 they had the same standard deviation to control variability across parameters. Setting a standard
148 deviation of 0.15 for all parameters was necessary to obtain a sufficiently large model population
149 with both electrical and mechanical features compatible with experimentally observed features.
150 The scaling factors followed thus a normal distribution with a mean equal to 1 and a standard
151 deviation of 0.15. System complexity led to a large number of interactions between parameter
152 changes, which add to parameter variability in determining output variability. As a consequence,
153 the chosen range of parameter variability led to a very broad population of outputs, whose
154 boundaries exceeded experimentally observed values. Thus, model refinement was performed by
155 eliminating profiles out of boundaries for healthy myocytes, leading to a population of 190 models
156 whose output matched experimentally observed values of electrophysiological and mechanical
157 properties listed in Tables S4 and S5. See supplementary material for additional details. The HF
158 myocyte population was generated from the healthy one by changing the parameters scaling
159 factors as detailed in the previous paragraph. Model refinement was applied to this population by
160 eliminating profiles characterized by values exceeding ± 3 SD from the population mean. The

161 remaining 190 models had electrophysiological and mechanical properties consistent with the
162 heterogeneities among experiments (Tables S6, S7 and S8).

163 As opposed to comparison between fully deterministic models, the comparison between
164 model populations allows to extract significant parameters by statistical methods. This makes
165 simulations outcome robust with respect to natural variability, thus increasing its predictive value.

166

167 **2.3. Biomarkers in model output**

168 The following electrophysiological, Ca^{2+} handling and mechanical properties (biomarkers)
169 were measured during stimulation at steady-state in each condition: action potential duration at
170 90% of repolarization (APD_{90}), cytosolic Ca^{2+} transient (CaT) amplitude (CaTA) and developed
171 force (DevF), calculated as the difference between systolic and diastolic Ca^{2+} and force values
172 respectively, time to peak force (TTP), and times at 50% and 90% recovery from peak force (RT_{50}
173 and RT_{90}). CaT duration was measured at 80% of decay (CaTD_{80}); total duration of the force
174 twitch, including contraction and relaxation, was calculated as $\text{TD}_{90}=\text{TTP}+\text{RT}_{90}$. For
175 quantification of the electromechanical window (EMw), i.e the difference between the duration
176 of the mechanical and electrical systoles, we used TD_{90} and APD_{90} ($\text{EMw}=\text{TD}_{90}-\text{APD}_{90}$). The
177 total net charge transferred during repolarization (Q_{Total}) was obtained by integrating the total
178 membrane current (algebraic summation of individual currents) after the AP upstroke. Q_{Total} was
179 normalized to APD_{90} ($Q_{\text{Total}}/\text{APD}$), thus obtaining an index corresponding to the mean value for
180 net membrane current over repolarization.

181 We used vulnerability to EADs as a marker of electrical instability. The protocol to this
182 end included an EAD-inducing “perturbation” consisting of a lower stimulation frequency (0.25
183 Hz) and decreased I_{Kr} conductance (to simulate the effect of dofetilide), as in Margara et al. [10]
184 study. A 40% reduction in I_{Kr} , emulating the decrease caused by 0.01 μM dofetilide, provided the
185 suitable conditions to induce EADs in failing myocytes but not in the healthy ones.

186

187

188 **3. RESULTS**

189 **3.1. From an in silico heart failure electro-mechanical cellular model to a**
190 **virtual population**

191 The integration of cellular mechanics in the action potential model of a ventricular myocyte
192 allowed to explore the whole excitation-contraction coupling process that starts with the electrical
193 activation of cell membrane and leads to a contraction force, being Ca^{2+} the intermediate agent.
194 Figure 1 compares action potential (AP), Ca^{2+} transient (CaT) and active force in healthy (black)
195 and failing (red) cardiomyocytes at 1 Hz. The three upper panels represent the output with the
196 mean value of parameters in each condition (baseline models). HF myocytes had prolonged APD,
197 smaller and slower CaT, leading to smaller and slower contraction/relaxation. Notably, the
198 reduction in force did not match the one of CaT, reflecting the increment in myofilament
199 sensitivity to Ca^{2+} . These differences observed between healthy and failing myocytes at 1 Hz were
200 more relevant at larger heart rates, particularly in developed force (see next section).

201

202

203 Figure 1. Comparison between healthy (H) and heart failure (HF) myocytes at 1 Hz for action
204 potential, Ca^{2+} and force transients. A) mean of the two myocyte populations; B) individual
205 myocytes in the two populations.

206

207 Figure 1B compares the healthy population of 190 myocytes with the failing one, i.e. it
208 includes variability in profiles. Albeit the same parameter variability was applied to both model
209 populations, profiles variability differed between the healthy and HF population.

210 Firstly, within each condition, variability was larger for mechanical than for
211 electrophysiological outputs (Supplementary Figure S2). Indeed, mechanical constraints
212 dominated in restricting the initial population of 1000 models to that producing outputs within the
213 physiological range. Notably, there was not a specific range of mechanical parameters leading to
214 physiological phenotypes; mechanical responses varied instead as a consequence of multiple
215 interactions between model parameters. This suggests that the excitation-contraction coupling
216 process has a higher degree of non-linearity (complexity) as compared to excitation itself.

217

218
219 Figure 2. Comparison of duration intervals in healthy (H) and failing myocytes (HF). Action
220 potential duration (APD₉₀), intracellular Ca^{2+} transient duration (CaTD₈₀), total duration of the
221 isometric twitch force (TD₉₀), and electromechanical window (EMw).

222

223 APD₉₀, CaTD₈₀, and TD₉₀ values, represented in Figure 2, were larger in failing than in
224 healthy myocytes and variability within the population increased in the HF one. The EMw was
225 also prolonged in HF because the force transient was more prolonged than APD. EMw variance,
226 contributed by both TD and APD variabilities, was large and it strongly increased in HF. The

227 increased variances in the HF model result from an increased sensitivity of the model to
228 perturbations; experiments have also shown a larger APD variability in HF [21–23].

229

230 3.2. Rate-dependency of electro-mechanics

231 Consistent with experimental observations, the response of healthy myocytes to an increase
232 in heart rate was APD shortening and an increase of CaT amplitude (CaTA) to generate a larger
233 developed force (DevF) (Figure 3), the latter effect defining a positive FFR slope.

234 In HF, the reverse APD rate-dependency was steeper (Figure 3A), thus APD difference
235 with healthy myocytes decreased as rate increased. At low frequencies, APD difference between
236 both conditions was so elevated that reflected an increased sensitivity of failing myocytes, with
237 longer APDs, to perturbations [24].

238 The rate-dependency of CaTA, positive and steep in healthy myocytes, was almost
239 completely lost in HF ones (Figure 3B). Accordingly, the FFR slope was markedly depressed in
240 HF, with a tendency to become negative between 1.5 and 2 Hz (Fig 2C). The flat HF DevF curve
241 intersected the healthy one at about 0.7 Hz, suggesting that contractile deficit in failing myocytes
242 may be minimal, or even reversed at very slow rates. A flat curve was also observed with CaTA
243 (Figure 3B) in failing myocytes but it did not intersect the healthy one; this implies that factors
244 other than Ca^{2+} availability may account for the peculiar rate-dependency of DevF.

245

246

247 Figure 3. Rate-dependency in healthy (H) and failing populations of myocytes (HF). A) Action
248 potential duration (APD₉₀), B) Ca^{2+} transient amplitude (CaTA) and C) developed force (DevF)
249 variation with frequency.

250 At this point, it is important to remark that blunted HF curves in CaT and force were not
 251 observed when we used the electrophysiological O'Hara model [25] instead of the most updated
 252 ToR-ORd [16] version (Supplementary Figure S1). One of the main differences between the two
 253 AP models is I_{CaL} formulation. In addition, LTCC are distributed between T-tubular and
 254 sarcolemmal subspaces only in ToR-ORd model, which facilitated the implementation of
 255 detubulation for the HF model.

256
 257 Figure 4. Impact of frequency on mechanics in the population. A) Force-frequency relationship
 258 (FFR) curves of all the cell models, B) Comparison of FFR slopes in frequency intervals between
 259 healthy and failing cells. C) Effect of frequency on twitch contraction biomarkers: diastolic force
 260 (DiastF), time to peak force (TTP), time from peak force to 90% relaxation (RT₉₀). Data points
 261 represent means \pm SD of the population of models (H: healthy cells, HF: cells with heart failure).

262
 263 Figure 4A displays the rate-dependency of DevF of the different cells from the population.
 264 Although all the curves essentially reproduced the mean FFR differences between healthy and
 265 HF, we can observe the variability in curve steepness in each frequency range. The derivative of

266 the FFR curves (“local” slope) was statistically smaller in HF than in healthy myocytes at all rates
267 with more significant differences at intermediate ones (Figure 4B). This figure also shows that
268 FFR derivative decreased at higher rates in both populations, as expected from the “saturating”
269 effect of rate; however, saturation was achieved at lower rates in HF.

270 Diastolic force, the minimum component of DevF, increased with rate (Figure 4C, left
271 panel) and more steeply in HF. At the highest frequency of stimulation (2Hz), the marked increase
272 of diastolic force in HF caused an average difference of 2.6 kPa (nine-fold larger) between failing
273 and healthy myocytes. Rate-dependency of diastolic Ca^{2+} was also steeper in HF myocytes
274 (Supplementary Figure S4), but the difference at 2 Hz amounted to a maximum of 60%. The
275 disproportionate increase of diastolic force at fast rates in HF is the consequence of increased
276 sarcomere Ca^{2+} affinity, as the simulation of HF without the increased sarcomere affinity confirms
277 (Figure 4C, dotted line). While enhancing contraction at slow rates, the latter may limit Ca^{2+}
278 reuptake by the store and relaxation when diastolic intervals are critically shortened.

279 Besides DevF, force transient duration parameters were quantified at different rates (Figure
280 4C). TTP decreased with rate and the effect was more marked in HF myocytes, which had longer
281 TTP compared to healthy cells. Similarly, RT_{90} was longer in HF and it also decreased with
282 stimulation rate in both myocyte types.

283

284 **3.3. Mechanisms determining CaTA and DevF changes**

285 To understand the factors underlying the HF-related changes in contraction and its rate-
286 dependency (FFR), we started from the HF model and systematically restored one input parameter
287 at a time to its healthy (pre-remodeling) value. In this analysis we focused on functions relevant
288 to Ca^{2+} handling (SERCA, NCX, RyRs, SR leak, T-tubules and $[\text{Ca}]_{\text{T50}}$) because CaTA and DevF
289 rate-dependency were correlated. The term “restoration” here means correction of the change
290 induced by HF; i.e. enhancement if function was lost and vice versa.

291 The effect of some parameters was similar at all rates; other parameters also changed rate-
292 dependency (curve steepness) (Figure 5). Parameters restoration similarly affected CaTA and

293 DevF (Figure 5A and 5B), with the exception of $[Ca]_{T50}$. The latter offset the CaTA curve upward
 294 and the DevF one downward, as expected from a decrease in sarcomere Ca^{2+} buffering power and
 295 thin-filament activation respectively. To highlight modulation of FFR, curves were normalized
 296 for the value at 0.5 Hz (Figure 5C). SERCA restoration was most effective in recovering CaTA
 297 and DevF rate-dependency toward the healthy condition, followed by restoration of NCX and
 298 $[Ca]_{T50}$ (Figure 5C). The effect of restoring other parameters was similar at all rates (no change
 299 in slope). T-tubule restoration changed both CaTA and DevF slightly, rate-independently and,
 300 unexpectedly, in the negative direction. However, at the dyadic level, CaTA increased and TTP
 301 decreased after T-tubule restoration as expected (Supplementary Figure S5).

302

303

304 Figure 5. Modulation of frequency dependency by Ca^{2+} dynamics factors in a failing myocyte. A)
 305 intracellular Ca^{2+} transient amplitude (CaTA), B) Force-frequency relationship of absolute
 306 developed force (DevF) and C) normalized to DevF at 0.5 Hz. Six parameters were restored, one
 307 at a time, taking into account that, in the HF model, myofilament Ca^{2+} sensitivity is increased (
 308 $[Ca]_{T50}$ reduction by 30%), 46% of T-tubules are lost, SERCA maximal activity is downregulated

309 by 55%, NCX is upregulated by 60%, RyRs channel sensitivity to SR Ca^{2+} is increased ($K_{\text{rel,Ca}}$
310 reduction by 20%), and Ca^{2+} leak from the SR compartment (SR leak) is increased by 30%.

311

312 **3.4. Susceptibility to EADs**

313 Under the conditions used to facilitate EADs (dofetilide + low rate), the latter never
314 occurred in the healthy model population. The same conditions induced EADs in 59 out of 190
315 cells of the HF population. Under these conditions, I_{Kr} was reduced by 40% and parameter
316 variability within the failing population contributed to further decrease the already reduced
317 repolarization reserve in HF and increased EAD vulnerability. Figure 6A shows the output of the
318 model population; EADs occurred at the transition between phase 2 and 3 of the action potential
319 and were consistently associated with secondary Ca^{2+} and force transients. There were small
320 differences in maximum DevF between cells with and without repolarization abnormalities, but
321 aftercontractions concomitant with EADs might be compromising lusitropy and cellular
322 relaxation.

323 Myocytes within the HF population were classified in two groups, according to EAD
324 development or not, to compare their input parameters. Whereas sarcomere properties did not
325 differ between the two subpopulations (not shown) a panel of ionic conductances set the
326 conditions for EADs to occur. Figure 5B compares vulnerable and resistant myocytes to EADs
327 for the scale factors of electrophysiological input parameters because this classification divided
328 each parameter distribution of the population into two new subpopulation distributions
329 (Supplementary Figure S3). To better explore the difference between groups, a statistical analysis
330 was performed with the Wilcoxon rank sum test by MATLAB and $p < 0.05$ was considered
331 significant. However, as the use of statistical significance tests to interpret simulation results are
332 considered inappropriate, we also focused on the magnitude of the differences observed [26].
333 Vulnerable myocytes were characterized by significantly larger I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} and NCX, and smaller
334 I_{Kr} , I_{NaK} and SERCA activity.

335

336 Figure 6. Effect of 0.01 μ M dofetilide on cellular electro-mechanics of the failing population
 337 stimulated at 0.25 Hz. A) Action potential, intracellular Ca^{2+} transient (CaT) and force time
 338 courses, displaying early afterdepolarizations (EAD) and aftercontractions. B) Comparison
 339 between vulnerable (EADs) and resistant (no EADs) myocytes in terms of the scale factors
 340 (distributions) applied to the ionic conductances.

341

342 Whereas the pattern of sarcolemmal conductances in vulnerable myocytes is fully
 343 consistent with the notion of reduced repolarization reserve, that reduced SERCA activity should
 344 promote EADs was less obvious and raises the question, of therapeutic relevance, of whether
 345 SERCA enhancement may be expected to prevent EADs in the context of HF. Thus, we tested
 346 whether a 2-fold SERCA enhancement in vulnerable HF myocytes would, on its own, reduce the
 347 incidence of EADs. The number of HF models developing EADs was reduced by 71% after
 348 increasing SERCA activity by a factor of 2 (Figure 7A). The incidence and amplitude of

349 secondary force transients (aftercontractions) was consequently reduced. Notably, the amplitude
350 of the main force twitch was barely affected by this level of SERCA enhancement, only a bit
351 smaller and shorter, at least at low stimulation frequencies. At faster heart rates, doubling SERCA
352 increased force as a consequence of the prominent increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} (Supplementary
353 Figure S6), highlighting that the effect of SERCA modulation is frequency-dependent.

354 A further question concerns the mechanism by which SERCA enhancement may suppress
355 EADs developed in failing myocytes. To address it, we analyzed in detail the time course of
356 membrane potential, subsarcolemmal (ss, left) and bulk cytosolic (i, right) Ca^{2+} concentrations
357 and relevant membrane currents in one representative HF myocyte before (red) and after (blue)
358 EADs suppression by SERCA enhancement (Figure 7B). Furthermore, Figure S8, discussed in
359 the Supplement, shows the contribution of individual fluxes (to and from the cytosol) to the $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$
360 balance at steady-state (total influx=total efflux) in HF myocytes just before the EAD, after the
361 perturbation induced by an EAD and at steady-state after SERCA enhancement (EADs inhibited).

362 A close analysis of the timing and direction of events during the AP plateau (insets of
363 Figure 7B) indicates that the EAD was triggered by I_{CaL} reactivation; indeed, the maximal dV/dt
364 of the EAD coincides with the secondary $I_{\text{CaL,ss}}$ peak and, because of its outward direction, the
365 I_{NCX} change must be voltage-driven (i.e. an EAD consequence) as opposed to Ca^{2+} -driven.

366 An increment in SERCA activity enhanced cytosolic Ca^{2+} clearance (decreased $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$) and
367 elevated SR Ca^{2+} content (increased $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{NSR}}$), thus boosting the release flux during the action
368 potential plateau. Because of their delayed equilibration, the net effect of SERCA enhancement
369 differed between the two subcompartments: $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{ss}}$ was increased and $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ was decreased. The
370 higher $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{ss}}$ increased the proportion of Ca^{2+} -bound (inactivated) I_{CaL} channels, thus preventing
371 the secondary rise in I_{CaL} . On the other hand, the decrease in $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ reduced forward-mode NCX
372 operation (less inward I_{NCX}) in the non-dyadic sarcolemma. As a consequence of both these
373 events, SERCA enhancement alone abolished I_{CaL} reactivation, and the resulting EAD in a
374 significant proportion of cells.

375 Despite the comprehensive explanation presented with Figure 7, the close-loop system
376 hampers the understanding of the real contribution of some parameters. Breaking the loop,

377 possible by means of computer simulations, confirmed the relevant role of I_{CaL} . The I_{CaL} computed
 378 with the HF model until the time of EAD takeoff was fed to the SERCA enhanced model and then
 379 switched to the usual computation mode. Unlike EAD suppression obtained with SERCA
 380 enhancement, clamping a less inactivated I_{CaL} contributed to EAD development (Supplementary
 381 Figure S7).
 382

383

384 Figure 7. SERCA enhancement effect on failing cells with early afterdepolarizations (EADs). A)
385 Action potentials (AP) with EADs (first panel) that lead to aftercontractions in Ca^{2+} transient
386 (middle panel) and in twitch force (right panel). Some EADs disappear after 2-fold SERCA
387 enhancement (SERCA $_{++}$, blue). B) Example of EAD suppression after SERCA enhancement,
388 with changes in AP, currents, Ca^{2+} concentrations and fluxes contributing to repolarization
389 recovery: membrane potential (V_m), intracellular Ca^{2+} concentration ($[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$), Ca^{2+} stored in the
390 network and junctional sarcoplasmic reticulum compartments ($[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{NSR}}$ and $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{JSR}}$,
391 respectively), SR Ca^{2+} release (J_{rel}), L-type Ca^{2+} current (I_{CaL}) and $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger (NCX).
392 Subscripts ‘ss’ and ‘i’ refer to the dyadic space (T-tubules) and bulk cytosolic compartment
393 respectively.

394

395 Myocytes in which the 2-fold SERCA enhancement alone was not enough to suppress
396 EADs had a different protein expression and function than those in which SERCA enhancement
397 had a positive effect. In a first attempt to analyze which parameters contributed to make the cell
398 EAD-prone even after SERCA stimulation, no individual parameter stood out as significantly
399 influential; this pointed to the influence of multiple parameter combinations instead. The effect
400 of combinations of parameters on the AP can be assessed by quantifying the “repolarization
401 reserve”. To this end, we considered the $Q_{\text{Total}}/\text{APD}$ ratio which is, by definition, positive
402 (outward) during monotonic repolarization. With the aim to test its predictive power, $Q_{\text{Total}}/\text{APD}$
403 was compared between EAD-resistant HF myocytes (without EADs), EAD-vulnerable ones in
404 which SERCA enhancement suppressed EADs (EAD suppression), and those in which EADs
405 persisted even after SERCA enhancement (EADs). Because EADs occurrence would strongly
406 bias the index, in this analysis myocytes were stimulated at 1 Hz and without I_{Kr} block to prevent
407 EADs occurrence in all groups.

408

409 Figure 8. Comparison of Q_{Total}/APD among the 3 groups of HF cells classified according to their
 410 response to SERCA enhancement: those without EADs (left), with EADs suppressed by SERCA
 411 enhancement (middle), with persistent EADs (right). Q_{Total}/APD was quantified in “unperturbed”
 412 conditions (1 Hz, no I_{Kr} blockade) and before SERCA enhancement.

413

414 Figure 8 shows that the largest Q_{Total}/APD was in EAD-resistant HF myocytes, the smallest
 415 when EADs persisted even after SERCA enhancement and it was intermediate when EADs
 416 occurred but could be suppressed by SERCA enhancement.

417

418 4. DISCUSSION

419 4.1. Main findings

420 This study approaches HF contractile and electrical abnormalities by a model integrating
 421 remodeling-induced changes in membrane electricity, intracellular Ca^{2+} dynamics, sarcomere
 422 function and disruption of the T-tubule sub-compartment.

423 Biological variability was reproduced by random scaling of individual input parameters to
 424 generate a population of models, each representing a virtual myocyte with properties dictated by
 425 the interaction among its unique set of components. This approach allows for robust assessment
 426 of the principal determinants of system’s response through statistical analysis applied to the
 427 population of virtual myocytes.

428 The average model output reproduced well known features of the failing myocardium,
429 including depressed contraction and slowed relaxation, flat FFR and increased vulnerability to
430 EADs. Systematic recovery of Ca^{2+} -related input parameters identified SERCA depression as the
431 main determinant of FFR flattening in HF, followed by NCX upregulation and increased Ca^{2+}
432 affinity of sarcomeres. SERCA depression (reducing force) and increased Ca^{2+} affinity of
433 sarcomeres (increasing force) were most influential in this condition.

434 Statistical analysis applied to the population of virtual myocytes allowed to identify which
435 input parameters significantly correlated with EADs vulnerability in HF. As expected,
436 conductance changes leading to an inward shift of the net membrane current at plateau potentials
437 (I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} and I_{NCX} increments, I_{Kr} and I_{NaK} decrements) positively correlated with EADs
438 incidence. Less expectedly, SERCA depression was also associated with a larger EADs incidence.
439 The sequence and direction of events just preceding an EAD identifies re-activation of I_{CaL} (in the
440 dyadic space) as the triggering mechanism, Ca^{2+} and I_{NCX} transients being the consequence of
441 membrane depolarization. Recovery of SERCA function increased systolic Ca^{2+} concentration in
442 the dyadic space, thus preventing I_{CaL} re-activation and the consequent EADs. Based on these
443 findings, SERCA enhancement in heart failure provides both electrical and mechanical benefits
444 and we suggest that the development of therapies targeting this protein would be valuable.

445

446 **4.2. Model validation**

447 The electrophysiological component of the HF model has been validated previously [1,21];
448 however, the increased complexity introduced by the sarcomeric dynamics and T-tubular changes
449 demands additional validation. The first verification confirmed that the electro-mechanical model
450 in healthy myocytes reproduced rate-dependency of contraction features (DevF, TTP and RT90)
451 fully consistent with measurements in human myocardium [27–29]. Secondly, the HF model
452 reproduced the main features of HF. In terms of electrophysiology an average APD prolongation
453 of 45%, increased APD variability and vulnerability to EADs agreed with experimental
454 observations [21,30]. The aberrant changes in intracellular Ca^{2+} dynamics and force transients

455 were also reproduced [31,32], with an average 50% depression in Ca^{2+} transients and slow
456 kinetics. The model output was quantitatively accurate in terms of force depression (50% to 80%
457 healthy myocytes) but despite changing kinetics accordingly, transient delays could be
458 overestimated [33–36]. Small differences in developed force between healthy and HF myocytes
459 have also been observed and we found that it can occur around 0.7 Hz, where both FFR curves
460 intersect. This crossing between healthy and HF FFR curves at low pacing rates has been
461 experimentally observed in right ventricular tissue and ischemic hearts [29,37].

462

463 **4.3 Electrophysiological consequences of HF**

464 Repolarization delay is a well-known consequence of myocardial remodeling in HF [38]. Because
465 it tends to increase intracellular Ca^{2+} content, APD prolongation might be seen as compensatory
466 (to the contractile defect); however, it entails a proarrhythmic increase in APD variability [39], in
467 which I_{NaL} is usually involved [40]. This variability, which was clearly captured by the model
468 (Figure 1), may be largely accounted for by the increase in APD [21]; nonetheless, a contribution
469 of instability in intracellular Ca^{2+} dynamics should be considered [32]. Analyzing such a
470 hypothesis in detail was not among the aims of the present work, however, it may represent a
471 future use of the model.

472 A decrease (or negativization) in the EMw reportedly correlates with the risk of
473 arrhythmias [15], possibly because of perturbation of the physiological mechano-electric
474 feedback [41]. However, in the present HF model, the EMw was increased instead (i.e., TD_{90}
475 prolonged more than APD_{90}). While EMw shortening has been proposed as a promising
476 biomarker to classify drugs in the torsadogenic risk group, our results imply that conditions
477 promoting EADs may be present in HF even if the EMw positivity is increased. Thus, as an
478 arrhythmia predictor, the EMw might be less sensitive in HF than in primary repolarization
479 abnormalities.

480 HF patients have a predisposition to develop ventricular arrhythmias, which may end in
481 sudden cardiac death, and EADs are considered a major trigger in their initiation [42,43]. A

482 negative FFR has been associated experimentally to arrhythmias [14], so we took advantage of
483 the results provided by the electro-mechanical HF model to draw conclusions on the cause of
484 EADs.

485 Because EADs mechanism is not unique, in the present HF model, no initial assumption
486 was made about the mechanisms facilitated by the abnormalities simulating HF. EADs may be
487 primarily “electrical”; i.e., they may reflect the abnormal interplay between membrane potential
488 trajectory (repolarization slowing) and I_{CaL} gating (recovery and reactivation within “window”
489 potentials) [44]. Under some conditions, EADs are associated instead with early spontaneous Ca^{2+}
490 release (SCR) events, thus reflecting SR instability [45].

491 The timing and direction of events during the AP plateau (insets of figure 7B) indicates that
492 the former mechanism supported EADs in this model. Indeed, whereas an SCR-triggered EAD
493 would have been aligned with an inward surge in I_{NCX} , the opposite was true (Figure 7). The
494 question then arises of which, among HF-associated abnormalities, facilitated I_{CaL} reactivation
495 during the action potential plateau. Figure 7 inset shows that, just prior to EAD takeoff,
496 repolarization was slightly slowed in HF, but the difference was small; therefore, a faster I_{CaL}
497 recovery from inactivation may also be crucial. An interpretation of its mechanism is suggested
498 by the effects of SERCA enhancement as follows.

499 I_{CaL} channels largely reside in T-tubules ($I_{CaL,ss}$), thus being exposed to the Ca^{2+} levels
500 peculiar of the dyadic space ($[Ca^{2+}]_{ss}$). SERCA enhancement substantially increased SR Ca^{2+}
501 content, CaT amplitude and, thus $[Ca^{2+}]_{ss}$ during the plateau phase (Figure 7 left panels), agreeing
502 with the well-known role of SERCA on Ca^{2+} homeostasis [46]. This, in turn, delayed the recovery
503 of $I_{CaL,ss}$ from Ca^{2+} -induced inactivation, hence suppressing the EAD. According to this
504 interpretation, SERCA depression, with the resulting reduction of SR Ca^{2+} content, would be an
505 important determinant of EADs vulnerability in HF.

506 Although still compatible with SERCA depression, events occurring in the non-dyadic
507 intracellular space (Figure 7 right) are not easily related to EAD triggering. For instance, EAD
508 suppression by SERCA enhancement coincided with lowering of $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ and a sizable increase in
509 I_{CaLi} , both unsuitable to suppress EAD triggering. Nonetheless the reduction in (inward) I_{NCXi}

510 resulting from SERCA enhancement might still contribute to set the stage for EAD suppression.
511 Indeed, it has been pointed out that the generation of EADs in a myocyte may requires two
512 conditions: the presence of a “bistable” behavior of membrane potential plus a triggering
513 “oscillator” [47]. In tissue, either EADs synchronization across multiple cells, or reduced
514 intercellular coupling, is further required to prevent EAD quenching by surrounding myocytes
515 [43]. While I_{CaLss} re-activation accounts for the latter, an inward shift of net membrane current
516 may add an “equilibrium” point at plateau potentials, as required for membrane potential
517 bistability.

518 To summarize, at least in the HF setting of the present model, EADs facilitation resulted
519 from: 1) an inward shift of net membrane current (I_{NCXi} and I_{NaL} enhancement, I_{Kr} and I_{NaK}
520 reduction) and 2) premature reactivation of I_{CaLss} . Accordingly, SERCA enhancement may reduce
521 HF EAD incidence by: 1) decreasing I_{NCXi} and 2) enhancing Ca^{2+} -dependent inactivation of I_{CaLss} ,
522 both consequences of improved Ca^{2+} compartmentalization within the SR. The antiarrhythmic
523 effect of SERCA enhancement has been previously attributed to improved Ca^{2+} compartmentation
524 within the SR, which may stabilize RyRs and prevent the organization of Ca^{2+} sparks into waves,
525 as reviewed in [48]. Instead of focusing on SR stability, the interpretation suggested by the present
526 results points to modulation of membrane electrophysiology (i.e., increased I_{CaL} inactivation).
527 Both mechanisms may contribute to the antiarrhythmic effect of SERCA enhancement, i.e., the
528 two interpretations are not mutually exclusive.

529 A 2-fold increase in SERCA activity was not enough to suppress EADs in all cell models,
530 which suggests that suitable combinations of the other HF-induced abnormalities, all concocting
531 to shift Q_{Total}/APD inward, destabilized repolarization beyond reversibility. The correlation
532 between Q_{Total}/APD and EADs inducibility illustrates this concept. Genetic differences in the
533 conductances contributing to mean Q_{Total}/APD may support interindividual variability in
534 arrhythmia susceptibility.

535 Overall, the analysis of the factors leading to EADs generation and its suppression by
536 SERCA enhancement supports the validity of a conceptual scheme, proposed by Qu et al. [47],
537 borrowed from the theory of non-linear dynamics.

538 The beneficial effects of SERCA stimulation are known for improving intracellular Ca^{2+}
539 clearance and consequently enhancing contraction [49,50]. Although the analysis of SERCA
540 enhancement did not revealed an increase in force under EAD conditions, other conditions such
541 as an increase in heart rate showed that improvement. Our results suggest additional benefits of
542 SERCA enhancement by reducing ventricular arrhythmias generated by EADs, although restoring
543 deficient SERCA might also reduce arrhythmogenic cardiac alternans as explored by Cutler et al.
544 [51].

545

546 **4.4. Contractile consequences of HF**

547 As mentioned in the model validation section, the main contractile features of HF were
548 reproduced by the model. Of particular interest is the rate-dependency of developed force (FFR).
549 A positive FFR, observed within physiological ranges in all species and which is more
550 pronounced in large mammals [52], represents the component of cardiac adaptation to stress
551 intrinsic to the myocardium, i.e. independent from neurohumoral regulation. Along with APD
552 shortening, it is important in the preservation of stroke volume at high heart rates [27] and its loss
553 contributes to the HF syndrome [29,37]. The changes responsible for FFR may also lead to an
554 acceleration of the force transient, including its development (TTP) and decay (RT90) [27–29];
555 all these aspects were reproduced by the healthy myocyte model and were impaired in the HF
556 one. Rate-dependencies of force and force kinetics are not necessarily linked. Indeed, Mashali et
557 al. [29] reported FFR changes but no significant differences in TTP over the whole frequency
558 range nor differences between healthy and failing myocardium. However, TTP differences
559 between detubulated cells and cells with a dense t-system have been experimentally observed
560 [28], which suggests that elevated TTP results from Ca^{2+} rise delay because of impaired SR Ca^{2+}
561 release provoked by the loss of the T-tubular structure. In fact, we demonstrated by means of
562 computational simulations that FFR is highly related to Ca^{2+} dynamics and that it can be
563 modulated by ionic mechanisms.

564 Although impaired Ca^{2+} handling and abnormal FFR are clearly related [27], there are still
565 some controversies about the mechanisms primarily involved, which would represent the best
566 targets to restore normal cardiac function in the failing myocardium. This model incorporates all
567 the elements known to be involved in modulating FFR, thus allowing to test their relevance in the
568 HF dysfunction. T-tubules define the dyadic space, where Ca^{2+} -induced I_{CaL} inactivation mostly
569 occurs. The latter, in turn, is crucial in maintaining the Ca^{2+} influx/efflux balance at various rates.
570 RyRs Ca^{2+} -sensitivity sets the gain of EC-coupling. The buffering effect of sarcomeres strongly
571 affects the rates of cytosolic Ca^{2+} clearance and mechanical relaxation, clearly relevant to cope
572 with rate-dependent changes in the electrical and mechanical “duty cycles” (systole/cycle length).
573 The balance between SERCA, leak and NCX fluxes sets the SR Ca^{2+} content and is rate-
574 dependent.

575 The analysis shown in Figure 5 allows to identify which among these elements, if restored
576 by therapy, i.e. correction of the change induced by HF, would afford the largest improvement in
577 FFR. Restoration of SERCA activity was most effective in recovering FFR, followed by
578 restoration of NCX and of $[\text{Ca}]_{\text{T50}}$. Modulation of the other elements changed force development
579 at all rates, but failed to affect FFR appreciably. Cytosolic Ca^{2+} is needed to activate myofilament
580 contraction and SERCA and NCX restoration improved FFR by increasing free cytosolic Ca^{2+} .
581 Although it is known that detubulation alters Ca^{2+} release [53], our results do not highlight
582 recovery of either T-tubules or RyR facilitation as major factors in the recovery of FFR. Notably,
583 this contrasts with experimental observations in rats [54]. The direction of changes fits with logic
584 for all the elements except T-tubules restoration. Whereas the latter was expected to increase
585 CaTA, DevF and restore FFR [54], in the non-dyadic space CaTA was slightly reduced and force
586 (DevF and FFR) remained almost unchanged. However, in the dyadic space T-tubular recovery
587 increased CaTA and shortened TTP, which is more in line with the experimental observations
588 [28,54]. This suggests that the role of the T-tubular dyadic compartment in setting overall
589 myocyte contractile function may be underestimated in the present model. Because the impact of
590 dyadic space crucially depends on the interaction among multiple variables the system response
591 may be difficult to interpret and predict and extrapolate across different species. Thus, while some

592 discrepancies suggest to interpret these particular results with caution, it does not argue against
593 the model predictivity in general.

594 Rate-dependency of diastolic force has been recently measured in human trabeculae and
595 found to be similar between non-failing and failing muscles [29]. However, our results show a
596 rate-dependent increase in diastolic force in HF as in intracellular Ca^{2+} . Diastolic force build-up
597 at faster heart rates reflects incomplete diastolic relaxation as diastolic time shortens. Two factors,
598 both represented in the model, contribute to rate-dependent diastolic dysfunction: slower Ca^{2+}
599 reuptake into the SR (due to SERCA dysfunction and increased SR leak) and slower Ca^{2+}
600 dissociation from sarcomeres (with increased Ca^{2+} affinity). In agreement with [55,56], our results
601 show elevated diastolic Ca^{2+} due to SERCA downregulation but also due to NCX upregulation,
602 both peculiar of HF remodeling.

603

604 **4.5 Practical relevance**

605 Possibly the finding of greater practical relevance in the present work is that recovery of
606 SERCA function alone may, albeit through different mechanisms, improve contractile
607 performance and reduce EADs-triggered arrhythmogenesis in the failing heart. However, this
608 finding does not imply that SERCA is the only contributor, as the present study focused on
609 SERCA to exploit the potential of this factor. SERCA enhancement has been initially attempted
610 in HF by gene therapy and failed because of difficulties in construct delivery [50]. Nonetheless,
611 recently developed small-molecule SERCA activators are endowed with significant ino-lusitropic
612 effect in acute HF patients [49,57], notably in the absence of proarrhythmia. This provides a
613 realistic opportunity of pharmacological SERCA enhancement.

614

615 **4.6 Limitations**

616 Active force has been measured under isometric conditions (no sarcomere shortening), thus
617 it represents the maximal force developed at the specified sarcomere length (or maximal
618 elastance, Frank-Starling law). Isometric force has the advantage of being independent of

619 mechanical load, thus allowing direct comparison of data among different experimental settings.
620 However, this approach does not take into account the many consequences of sarcomere
621 shortening, which also contribute to muscle performance during physiological operation.
622 Especially in HF, prestretch effect on force generation and duration may change and the
623 mechano-electrical feedback might show important effects on the EMw at the organ level.

624 Despite the attempt to model the characteristic detubulation in HF, the approach used
625 showed some flaws in the mechanistic analysis of T-tubules effect. However, the model as a
626 whole firmly reproduced the electromechanical profiles of failing myocytes.

627 Nonetheless, once validated, a cellular HF electro-mechanical mode can be applied to a
628 wider range of conditions and implemented within tissue and organ models. The latter are required
629 to include the role of passive forces, which largely depend on tissue components providing
630 stiffness (e.g. collagen content) and chamber geometry. Although we did quantify diastolic active
631 force, passive force importantly contributes to diastolic behavior.

632 Despite these limitations, results of the present study highlighting the benefits of SERCA
633 stimulation are helpful to guide future investigations, especially those targeting SERCA protein
634 to improve cardiac output.

635

636 **Supplementary Material**

637

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643

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Supplementary Material

Insights from an Electro-Mechanical Heart Failure Cell Model: Role of SERCA Enhancement on Arrhythmogenesis and Myocyte Contraction

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1. SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS

1.1. Implementation of the cellular heart failure model

Electrophysiological heart failure remodeling, based on experimental observations, was applied to several ionic parameters according to Gomez et al. [1] and adapted to ToR-ORd model [2]. Table S1 modifications modulate the total function of each parameter (currents and fluxes) to reproduce either a change in expression or level of activity.

Table S1. Heart failure (HF) remodeling in ToR-ORd model.

Ionic parameter	% of change compared to ToR-ORd	Experimental references
I_{NaL}	130 %	[3]
τ_{hL}	180 %	[3]
I_{to}	40 %	[4]
I_{K1}	68 %	[5]
I_{NaK}	70 %	[5–7]
NCX	165 %	[8]
CaMKa	150 %	[9,10]
SERCA	45 %	[11]
J_{leak}	130 %	[12]
$K_{rel,Ca}$	80 %	[13]

The modified parameters are the maximum values of the late Na^+ current (I_{NaL}), the time constant of inactivation of the I_{NaL} (τ_{hL}), the transient outward current (I_{to}), the inward rectifier K^+ current (I_{K1}), the Na^+/K^+ pump current (I_{NaK}), the Na^+/Ca^{2+} exchanger (NCX), the fraction of active binding sites of the Ca^{+2} calmodulin-dependent protein kinase II (CaMKa), the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR) Ca^{2+} pump (SERCA), the SR Ca^{2+} leak (J_{leak}) and the sensitivity to $[Ca^{2+}]_{JSR}$ of the ryanodine receptors (Ca^{2+} sensitivity of $J_{rel,\infty}$, called $K_{rel,Ca}$).

Following the work by Sanchez-Alonso et al. [14], T-tubule loss was implemented in the heart failure ToR-ORd model. The initial distribution of $ICaL$ and NCX in dyadic (ss) and bulk (i) subspaces changes with detubulation. In healthy cells:

$$ICaL = 0.8 \cdot I_{CaL,ss} + 0.2 \cdot I_{CaL,i}$$

$$NCX_{ss} = 0.35 \cdot NCX \text{ and } NCX_i = 0.65 \cdot NCX$$

After 46 % of T-tubular loss, the presence of transmembrane proteins in the subsarcolemmal subspace decreases.

$$I_{CaL,ss} = 0.8 \cdot 0.54 \cdot 1.2 \cdot 0.9 \cdot I_{CaL,ss}$$

$$I_{CaL,i} = (0.2 + 0.46 \cdot 0.8) \cdot 0.85 \cdot 0.9 \cdot I_{CaL,i}$$

$$NCX_{ss} = 0.35 \cdot 0.54 \cdot NCX \text{ and } NCX_i = (0.65 + 0.35 \cdot 0.46) \cdot NCX$$

$$18.9\% NCX_{ss} + 81.1\% NCX_i$$

There is maximal CaMKII phosphorylation of $I_{CaL,i}$:

$$f_{CaLp_i} = 1$$

And the link between LTCCs and RyRs is also lost, with a decrease in Ca^{2+} release:

$$J_{rel} = 0.54 \cdot 1.5378 \cdot ((1.0 - f_{J_{relp}}) \cdot J_{relnp} + f_{J_{relp}} \cdot J_{relp});$$

1.2. Selection of the electrophysiological model

An important cellular property analyzed in this study was the force-frequency relationship (FFR) and it was a critical factor to choose the electrophysiological model to couple with mechanics. ToR model [2] is an improved and updated version of the human ORd model [15] with similar outputs at 1 Hz. However, we found that ToR model better reproduced frequency stimulation effects in healthy myocytes because the slope of this curve was less steep. Additionally, when we implemented heart failure ionic remodeling, the blunted or negative FFR was better represented with ToR model than with ORd, which showed a steeper positive curve as shown in Fig. S1.

Fig. S1. Comparison of ORd and ToR models without detubulation. A) Ca^{2+} transient amplitude (CaTA) and B) developed force (DevF) variations with frequency in healthy and failing myocytes (HF).

1.3. Generation of a population of models

To build the initial population of models, the same uncertainty ($\pm 30\%$ variability) was applied to the 28 parameters of the electro-mechanical model. Table S2 shows 18 parameters belonging to the electrophysiological ToR model [2].

The remaining 11 parameters (Table S3) were mechanical properties of the active tension Land model [16]. Two parameters, n_{Tm} and k_u , had the nominal values reported by Margara et al. [17], which were adjusted to get a physiological twitch tension with the Land model coupled to ToR.

Table S2. Electrophysiological parameters subjected to uncertainty.

#	Parameter	Description	Nominal value
1	G_{Na}	Fast Na^+ maximal conductance	11.7802 mS/ μ F
2	P_{CaL}	L-type Ca^{2+} current permeability	8.3757e-05 cm/s
3	G_{to}	Transient outward K^+ maximal conductance	0.16 mS/ μ F
4	G_{NaL}	Late Na^+ maximal conductance	0.0279 mS/ μ F
5	G_{Kr}	Rapid delayed rectifier K^+ conductance	0.0321 mS/ μ F
6	G_{Ks}	Slow delayed rectifier K^+ conductance	0.0011 mS/ μ F
7	G_{K1}	Inward rectifier K^+ conductance	0.6992 mS/ μ F
8	G_{bK}	Background K^+ permeability	0.0189 mS/ μ F
9	K_{NCX}	Maximal Na^+/Ca^{2+} exchanger current	0.0034 μ A/ μ F
10	K_{NaK}	Maximal Na^+-K^+ pump activity	15.4509
11	P_{bNa}	Background Na^+ permeability	1.9238e-8 cm/s
12	P_{bCa}	Background Ca^{2+} permeability	5.9194e-8 cm/s
13	K_{pCa}	Maximal sarcolemmal Ca^{2+} pump current	0.0005 μ A/ μ F
14	G_{ClCa}	Ca-activated Cl^- current conductance	0.2843 mS/ μ F
15	G_{Clb}	background Cl^- conductance	1.98e-3 mS/ μ F
16	$J_{RyR,max}$	SR Ca^{2+} release maximal flux factor	1.00
17	$J_{SERCA,max}$	SR Ca^{2+} uptake maximal flux factor	1.00
18	$J_{Leak,max}$	SR Ca^{2+} leak maximal flux factor	1.00

Table S3. Mechanical parameters subjected to uncertainty.

#	Parameter	Description	Nominal value
19	n_{Tm}	Troponin-Myosin binding site cooperativity	2.4 (*)
20	$[Ca^{2+}]_{T50_ref}$	Ca-troponin half-activation	0.805 μ F
21	T_{ref}	Maximal active tension at resting length	120 kPa
22	k_{uw}	Crossbridge rate (U->W)	0.182 /ms
23	k_{ws}	Crossbridge rate (W->S)	0.014 /ms
24	k_{TRPN}	Ca-troponin unbinding rate	0.1 /ms
25	n_{TRPN}	Ca-troponin cooperativity	2
26	k_u	Myosin binding site unblock rate	0.04 /ms (*)
27	$TRPN_{50}$	CaTRPN in steady-state	0.35
28	r_w	Steady-state ratio W/(U+W)	0.5
29	r_s	Steady-state duty ratio	0.25

*Margara et al. readjustments [17]

1.4. Calibration of the population

The calibration process involved two steps, an electrophysiological and a mechanical calibration, which were separated because we needed to make mechanical limits more flexible to get a large group of cells.

For the electrophysiological calibration, action potential (AP) and Ca^{2+} transient (CaT) properties determined the constraints for endocardial cells phenotype within physiological ranges as done by Passini et al. [18]. After this first screening, 981 out of 1000 cells were accepted because they satisfied all the biomarkers ranges. Rejected cells had one or more properties out of limits.

Table S4. Upper and lower limits for electrophysiological biomarkers.

Biomarker		Min value	Max value
APD₄₀ (ms)	AP duration at 40% of repolarization	85	320
APD₅₀ (ms)	AP duration at 50% of repolarization	110	350
APD₉₀ (ms)	AP duration at 90% of repolarization	180	440
Tri₉₀₋₄₀ (ms)	AP triangulation	50	150
dV/dt_{max} (mV/ms)	maximal upstroke velocity	150	1000
V_{peak} (mV)	peak voltage	10	55
RMP (mV)	Resting membrane potential	-95	-80
CTD₅₀ (ms)	CaT duration at 50% of recovery	120	420
CTD₉₀ (ms)	CaT duration at 90% of recovery	220	785
Syst Ca²⁺ (mM)	maximal intracellular [Ca ²⁺]	0.000262	0.00223
Diast Ca²⁺ (mM)	minimal intracellular [Ca ²⁺]	0	0.00040

These biomarkers were AP duration at 40, 50 or 90% of repolarization (APD_{40/50/90}), AP triangulation defined as the difference between APD90 and APD40 (Tri₉₀₋₄₀), maximal upstroke velocity (dV/dt_{max}), peak voltage (V_{peak}); resting membrane potential (RMP), CaT duration at 50 or 90% of recovery (CTD_{50/90}), and maximal and minimal intracellular [Ca²⁺] (Syst and Diast Ca²⁺).

For the mechanical calibration, several biomarkers extracted from the simulated isometric twitch were compared with human active force data. These biomarkers were maximum and minimum force values, time to peak force (TTP), and 50% and 95% recovery times from peak force (RT50 and RT95). The experimental ranges shown in Table S4 were indeed very restrictive and not a single cell model fall within limits. As in Land et al. [16], we used a function that summed distances (d) between each biomarker and its corresponding experimental ranges to obtain the cost function (d_t):

$$d_t = d(TTP, [147,172]) + d(RT50, [109,125]) + d(RT95, [291,377]) + \\ + 10d(\max(F), [15,25]) + 25 \min(F)$$

The distance was zero if the biomarker was within the range. Priority for minimal and maximal active force was given by applying weights (25 and 10, respectively). We accepted cells with a d_t < 5, a threshold which was enough to maintain biomarkers close to the experimental ranges and obtain a population of cells (Fig. S2).

Table S5. Upper and lower limits for mechanical biomarkers.

Biomarker		Min value	Max value
TTP (ms)	Time to peak force	147	172
RT50 (ms)	Time at 50% recovery from peak force	109	125
RT95 (ms)	Time at 90% recovery from peak force	291	377
maxF (kPa)	Maximum force	15	25
minF (kPa)	Minimum force	0	-

Fig. S2. Calibration of the non-failing population of cells. A) Time courses of action potential (AP), Ca^{2+} transient (CaT) and force from accepted and rejected cellular models. Only 190 parameter sets out of the initial 1000 variants were accepted after electromechanical calibration within physiological ranges (dark blue). B) Histograms of mechanical biomarkers before and after calibration: maximum (maxF) and minimum force (minF) values, time to peak force (TTP), and 50% and 95% recovery times from peak force (RT50 and RT95): Vertical red lines indicate ranges used in the cost function for mechanical calibration.

Table S6. Validation data from experiments. Force biomarkers ranges experimentally observed in HF cells and compared to healthy cells.

	DevF (kPa)		TTP (ms)		RT50 (ms)		Reference
H	13.7±1.8	HF/H	165±7	HF/H	116±6	HF/H	[19]
HF	10.0±1.5	0.73	186±5	1.13	117±6	1.01	
H	22.8±1.4	HF/H	157±10	HF/H	117±8	HF/H	[20]
HF	11.9±1.4	0.52	169±17	1.08	130±17	1.11	
H	25.9±3.9	HF/H	189±9	HF/H	137±5	HF/H	[21]
HF	13.9±2	0.54	216±8	1.14	147±6	1.07	
H	14.5±4.4	HF/H					[22]
HF	12.7±4.5	0.88					
H		HF/H					[23]
HF		0.77-0.81					
H	16.2±1.4	HF/H	203±6	HF/N	137±4	HF/N	[24]
HF	11.9±1.2	0.73	201±5	0.99	152±5	1.11	

H: healthy, HF: heart failure. Isometric developed force (DevF), time to peak force (TTP), and time at 50% recovery from peak force (RT_{50}).

Table S7. Validation data from experiments. Action potential biomarkers ranges experimentally observed in HF cells and compared to healthy cells.

	BCL (ms)	APD₉₀ (ms)		APD₈₀ (ms)		Reference
H	2000	649±101	HF/H	437±18	HF/H	[25]
HF		1038±223	1.6			
H	1000	330±16	HF/H	450±35	1.03	[26]
HF		382±18	1.16			
H	1000	301.3± 8	HF/H	437±18	HF/H	[27]
HF		439.6±36	1.46			
H	1000			437±18	HF/H	[28]
HF				450±35	1.03	

H: healthy, HF: heart failure. Action potential duration at 90% or 80% of repolarization (APD₉₀ and APD₈₀).

Table S8. Validation data from experiments. Intracellular Ca²⁺ biomarkers ranges experimentally observed in HF cells and compared to healthy cells.

	BCL (ms)	CaTP (ms)		CaTD (ms)		CaSyst (nM)		Reference
H	3000	33±6	HF/H	246±37	HF/H	596±80	HF/H	[29]
HF		53±5	1.61	569±48	2.31			
H	1000					596±80	HF/H	[30]
HF						333±26	0.56	
H	500			555±20	HF/H	506±25	HF/H	[31]
HF				664±42	1.20	407±16	0.8	
H	1000					804±197	HF/H	[11]
HF						398±58	0.5	

H: healthy, HF: heart failure. Time to peak of Ca²⁺ transient (CaTP), Ca transient duration measured at 80% or 50% of decay (CaTD), and systolic Ca²⁺ (CaSyst).

2. SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

2.1. Parameter distributions

Populations of models were built from parameter distributions. We applied a Gaussian function for setting the probability distribution for each parameter, but posterior analysis of population outputs, warped these distributions (Fig. S3). Firstly, calibration constrained the number of valid models, which affected the parameters by limiting their variability or by shifting mean values. Secondly, the study of EADs and the classification of models, analyzed the subgroups by evaluating parameters differences due to their redistribution. Fig. S3 illustrates, as an example, changes in the probability distributions of I_{Kr} conductance.

Fig. S3. Probability distributions of I_{Kr} scaling factor in the population of failing cells. Calibration (A) and classification (B) methods modify mean and variance of the original normal distribution.

Fig. S4. Rate-dependency of diastolic Ca^{2+} in healthy (H) vs failing (HF) myocytes.

The force-frequency relationship is related with intracellular Ca^{2+} , and diastolic Ca^{2+} dictated diastolic force rate-dependency (Fig. S4).

2.2. Restored parameters

The mechanistic analysis of HF involves the restoration of defective components. A more exhaustive investigation of the effects on intracellular Ca^{2+} and force was required to better understand detubulation (Fig. S5), SERCA enhancement at a different heart rate (1 Hz) from that of the study (Fig. S6), and the role of I_{CaL} in EAD development (Fig. S7).

Fig. S5. Effect of T-tubules restoration (TT restored) in a failing cell (HF). A) Dyadic Ca^{2+} ($[Ca^{2+}]_{ss}$) at 1 Hz, B) Force twitch at 1 Hz, C) Time to peak force (TTP) rate dependency.

Fig. S6. Effect of SERCA enhancement (SERCAx2) in the failing population on membrane potential (A), Ca^{2+} transient (B) and force (C) at 1 Hz.

Fig. S7. Relevant role of I_{CaL} , and its components ($I_{\text{CaL,ss}}$ and $I_{\text{CaL,i}}$) for the effect of SERCA enhancement (SERCA++) on EADs suppression in the heart failure model (HF). Currents were clamped from $t=0$ to EAD takeoff (dotted lines).

A break of the close-loop system in which many mechanisms act simultaneously in EAD generation helped to prove the relevant role of I_{CaL} , quite negligible so far. For that, I_{CaL} (I_{CaLi} + I_{CaLss}) computed by the HF with reduced SERCA model was fed to the enhanced SERCA model until the time of EAD takeoff. Then, computation of I_{CaL} was switched to the usual model mode. EAD development supported the idea that increased Ca^{2+} in the subspace and the consequent I_{CaL} reduction was relevant for the effect of SERCA enhancement on EADs suppression. This approach also suggested that both I_{CaL} components were relevant for EADs, as clamping them independently failed to induce the expected afterdepolarizations.

The contribution of individual fluxes (to and from the cytosol) to the $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ balance at steady-state (total influx=total efflux) in a HF myocyte just before the EAD, after the perturbation induced by an EAD and at steady-state after SERCA enhancement (EADs inhibited) is shown in Fig. S8. Ca^{2+} influx (to cytosol): the EAD's effect is compatible with decreased SR Ca^{2+} content, resulting from the EAD-induced Ca^{2+} release. The changes observed after SERCA enhancement are likely the result of increased Ca^{2+} induced inactivation of I_{CaL} and RyRs stabilization by improved Ca^{2+} compartmentation. Ca^{2+} efflux (from the cytosol): SR Ca^{2+} uptake (J_{up}) may be slightly facilitated by EAD-induced decrease in SR Ca^{2+} load and strongly increased, at the expense of NCX flux, by SERCA enhancement.

Fig. S8. Average global Ca^{2+} movements to the cytosol (influx) and from the cytosol (efflux) in HF myocytes (N=59) at steady-state before the EAD (Before EAD), just following it (EAD), and at steady-state after suppressing EADs by upregulating SERCA activity (SERCAx2 & EAD suppression). In steady-state conditions the influx/efflux ratio was 1.

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